

SEMANTIC AND DISCURSIVE ANALYSIS OF DETECTIVE FICTION “MR. MERCEDES” BY STEPHEN KING

Soliyev F.F.

Head of the Department of the Center "Cooperation for Peace", Armed Forces of the Republic of
Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13864891>

Abstract. *Discourse analysis and semantics of Mr. Mercedes cover analytical approaches used in the study of language and communication, particularly in the context of interrogations and criminal investigations of horrified mass murder. Discourse analysis involves examining the structure, content, and context of language use in order to understand how meaning is constructed and conveyed through communication (Bakhtin, 1981). In the context of interrogation, discourse analysis may focus on analyzing the linguistic patterns, speech acts, and rhetorical strategies employed by detectives and suspects during questioning. Researchers may examine the use of language features such as vocabulary choice, sentence structure, conversational turn-taking, and speech patterns. The article covers lexical choices, syntax and sentence structure, narrative voice and point of view, social and psychological aspects, cultural references and other linguistic domains.*

Keywords: *context of interrogations and criminal investigations, linguistic patterns, speech acts, rhetorical strategies, linguistic abilities.*

“Blood dripping from the bent grille and stippling the windshield”

Main part

Formal semantic models of conversation and their governing principles become the new and powerful asset for presenting linguistic evidence in the process of criminal investigation both in real life and detective fiction. According to Saeed (2016), semantics is the study of meaning communicated through language.

A person’s linguistic abilities are based on knowledge such as pronouncing words, constructing sentences, and the meaning of individual words and sentences. But defining words, according to Aher (2016), is not just a semantic exercise. It is also a metalinguistic process. The semantic part of defining a word involves establishing the general category and identifying differentiating characteristics of the basic component of a dictionary definition. However, there is still little or no study regarding the narratives of detectives, criminals, and suspects as a description of the vocabulary words in utterances and paragraphs.

Semantics in detective fiction is always plays crucial role for the author to express their thought colorfully and authentically (Hurford, 2007). Stephen King’s Mr. Mercedes is a detective novel that delves into the minds of both the investigator and the criminal, presenting complex narrative rich in linguistic and psychological depth. Author utilizes discourse of narration, description and argumentation to have connection with a reader. Through a discursive semantic analysis, we can uncover how King employs language to develop characters, advance the plot, and evoke emotional responses from readers. Semantic elements within the novel, focusing on how discourse shapes the narrative and contributes to the overarching themes of justice, morality, and human nature (Clark, 2015). From the beginning of the plot author exploits deep metaphorical

language patterns to make it vivid and colorful. For instance, “*Once more he was reminded of a shy mole peering from its hole. A lady mole with a bad case of bed head.*” (King, 2014) suggests bright and genuine picture of scene that evoke reader’s sense of excitement and interest.

Another example of the text taken from the first letter of the mysterious murder Brady Hartsfield to the retired constable Bill Hodges: “*It would be too bad if you started thinking your whole career had been a waste of time because the fellow who killed all those Innocent People “slipped through your fingers.”*” (King, 2014). Discourse analysis of the statement semantically offers both idiomatic expression of fail to catch and failure of law-enforcement agencies. In addition, it reveals social injustice and bias that provokes the readers to feel strong apathy and dislike.

Author describes scene of mass murder so convincingly as though it is based on real stories. King creatively illustrates last moment of fatal accident using compelling poetic and expressive discourse. “*Augie was shoved hard to the left, stumbled, recovered, and was pushed forward. A flying elbow struck his cheekbone just below his right eye and that side of his vision filled with bright Fourth of July sparkles. From the other eye he could see the Mercedes not just emerging from the fog but seeming to create itself from it.*” (King, 2014).

By analyzing the semantic layers in Mr. Mercedes, we can better understand the linguistic strategies King employs to create a compelling and multifaceted story. King applies semantic layers to develop characters and scenes. One of the key character Bill Hodges, the retired detective, is portrayed through a semantic field that emphasizes his intelligence, experience, and determination. His dialogue often includes investigative jargon and logical reasoning, reflecting his methodical approach to solving the case. For instance: “*He holds the letter in his hand, looking at the Andrew Wyeth print on the wall.*” presents that former detective investigates the paper of the letter he got from anonymous correspondent (King, 2014).

Protagonist is considered to be an experienced police officer with good analytical approach: “*New chemicals and computer-assisted scanning processes can pick up excellent fingerprints from paper, but Hodges knows that if he turns this letter in to Forensics, they will find no prints on it but his.*” (King, 2014).

Another semantic layer shown when Hodges interacts with his team, his language is precise and directive, aiming to gather and synthesize information effectively. On the contrary, Brady Hartsfield, the antagonist, is characterized through a semantic field that highlights his cunning, malice, and psychological instability. His internal monologues and external dialogues are laced with hidden meanings and manipulative language, illustrating his deceptive nature. An example of this is when Brady communicates with Hodges, using taunts and cryptic messages that both challenge and provoke the detective. This statement demonstrates cunning approach of the antagonist and his technology skills and experience: “*He knows that sending the letter was a risk, but not a very big one. He made up a prose style that’s completely different from his own. The chances of the old cop picking up anything useful from the letter are slim to nonexistent.*” (King, 2014).

Debbie’s Blue Umbrella is a slightly bigger risk, but if the old cop thinks he can trace him down that way, he’s in for a big surprise. Debbie’s servers are in Eastern Europe, and in Eastern Europe computer privacy is like cleanliness in America: next to godliness.” (King, 2014)

Supporting characters like Holly Gibney and Jerome Robinson add further layers to the semantic tapestry of the novel. Holly’s analytical and sometimes awkward speech patterns contrast

with Jerome's youthful, tech-savvy language, showcasing their unique contributions to the investigation. These semantic distinctions help to flesh out their characters and their roles within the story.

Semantic construction of the crime, investigation clues and evidence are another point to examine in order to clarify intended message of the author for the readers. As the consequence, the semantic presentation of clues and evidence is crucial aspect of detective fiction. In Mr. Mercedes, King carefully embeds clues within the narrative, using descriptive language that invites readers to piece together with the mystery alongside the protagonists. These clues and pieces of evidence are meticulously pieced together by Bill Hodges and his team, leading to the eventual identification and confrontation with Brady Hartsfield. The car becomes crucial piece of evidence. *"Two motor patrol cops found the Mercedes an hour after the killings. It was behind one of the warehouses that cluttered the lakeshore."* (King, 2014). The police discover that the car stolen from Olivia Trelawney, a woman who later commits suicide, partly due to the guilt of leaving her car keys in the ignition.

The letter sent by Brady reveals the aspects of his personality, and desire for control and manipulation. It later provides clues for Hodges to track down the killer. Another essential clue was found in killer's house by Hodges and his team where they discover Hartsfield's computer with incriminating evidence "plans for future attack".

Semantically the description of the crime scene where the Mercedes plows into a crowd is rich with sensory details and precise language, which not only sets the scene but also plants seed for later revelations. The dialogues during interviews and interrogations are key sites for discursive semantic analysis. When Hodges questions witnesses or suspects, the choice of words, tone, and context are all significant. These interactions often involve strategic questioning, asking leading questions where Hodges aims to elicit specific information while navigating the nuances of each individual's speech. The semantic choices in these dialogues reveal power dynamics, intentions, and hidden truths.

In addition, both Hodges and Brady have extensive internal monologues that provide insight into their thought processes. These monologues are semantically rich, offering a window into their motivations, fears, and plans. For instance, Brady's thoughts are often marked by a sinister and calculating tone, while Hodges' internal dialogue reflects his struggle with retirement and his drive to bring the killer to justice.

Thematic semantics, moral discourse, justice and morality are the other areas of research of the novel. The theme of justice is central to Mr. Mercedes, and this is reflected in the semantic choices throughout the novel. Hodges' pursuit of Brady is framed as a moral quest, with language that emphasizes righteousness and duty. Conversely, Brady's actions are depicted through a semantic lens that highlights their depravity and immorality. This contrast creates a clear moral dichotomy that underpins the narrative. Human Nature and Psychological. Depth King's exploration of human nature and psychological depth is evident in the semantic nuances of his character portrayals. The complex motivations of both the protagonists and the antagonist are revealed through their speech and thought patterns. For example, Brady's troubled past and psychological issues are subtly hinted at through his fragmented and erratic internal monologues, while Hodges' dialogues reflect his resilience and ethical steadfastness.

The novel also offers social commentary on issues such as mental health, technology, and societal disconnection. These themes are woven into the narrative through semantic choices that

reflect contemporary concerns. For instance, Brady's use of technology to stalk and terrorize his victims speaks to broader anxieties about privacy and the darker side of technological advancements.

Conclusion

Through discourse and semantic analysis, we have uncovered how Stephen King uses language to construct meaning, develop characters, and advance the plot in *Mr. Mercedes*. The semantic layers in the novel reveal intricate details about the characters' motivations, the nature of the crime and investigation, and the overarching themes of justice and morality. The examination highlights the importance of semantic considerations in detective fiction, illustrating how language not only conveys information but also shapes readers' perceptions and emotional responses. King's skillful use of semantics in *Mr. Mercedes* demonstrates how detective novels can be both entertaining and deeply thought-provoking. In conclusion, *Mr. Mercedes* serves as a prime example of how discourse and semantics can enrich our understanding of literary texts, offering insights into the complex interplay between language, meaning, and narrative (Storjohann, 2010). Through this analysis, we gain a deeper appreciation for Stephen King's craftsmanship and the enduring appeal of detective fiction.

REFERENCES

1. King, S. (2014). *Mr. Mercedes. #1*. Scribner.
2. Clark, S. (2015). Vector Space Models of Lexical Meaning. In S. Lappin & C. Fox (Eds.), *The Handbook of Contemporary Semantic Theory* (pp. 493-522): Wiley-Blackwell
3. Storjohann, P. (ed). (2010). *Lexical-Semantic Relations: Theoretical and practical perspectives*: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
4. Bakhtin, M. (1981). *Discourse in the Novel The Dialogic Imagination: Four Essays* (pp. 259-422). Austin: University of Texas Press.
5. Hurford, J. R., Heasley, B., & Smith, M. B. (2007). *Semantics: a coursebook* (2nd ed ed.). Cambridge [Cambridgeshire]: Cambridge University Press
6. Hurford, J. R., Heasley, B., & Smith, M. B. (2007). *Semantics: a coursebook* (2nd ed ed.). Cambridge [Cambridgeshire]: Cambridge University Press
7. Hurford, J. R., Heasley, B., & Smith, M. B. (2007). *Semantics: a coursebook* (2nd ed ed.). Cambridge [Cambridgeshire]: Cambridge University Press
8. Hurford, J. R., Heasley, B., & Smith, M. B. (2007). *Semantics: a coursebook* (2nd ed ed.). Cambridge [Cambridgeshire]: Cambridge University Press
9. Hurford, J. R., Heasley, B., & Smith, M. B. (2007). *Semantics: a coursebook* (2nd ed ed.). Cambridge [Cambridgeshire]: Cambridge University Press
10. Saeed, J. I. (2016). *Semantics in Linguistics, in Semantics (Fourth edition ed.)* (No. 2). Chichester, West Sussex [England] ; Malden, MA: Wiley Blackwell
11. Saeed, J. I. (2016). *Semantics in Linguistics, in Semantics (Fourth edition ed.)* (No. 2). Chichester, West Sussex [England] ; Malden, MA: Wiley Blackwell
12. Aher, M. (2016). *The Semantics of discourse as evidence*. In *Paper in Forensic Linguistics*: Tartu University, Estonia
13. Aher, M. (2016). *The Semantics of discourse as evidence*. In *Paper in Forensic Linguistics*: Tartu University, Estonia